

CHANGES IN BIODIVERSITY AND ITS IMPACT ON THE FOREST ECOSYSTEM

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ABSTRACT

Forests are biologically diverse systems but are however increasingly threatened as a result of deforestation, fragmentation, climate change and other stressors that can be linked to human activities. When biodiversity is lost, the strength and capacity of the ecosystems to provide essential goods and services become incapacitated in terms of scientific, educational, historical and cultural resources. This reviewed paper summarises the impact of biodiversity change on the forest ecosystem and briefly looked at mitigation measures to stop the ongoing trend.

KEYWORDS: Changes, biodiversity, forest, ecosystems, climate change.

INTRODUCTION

Biodiversity as a concept came into limelight in the 80s' as an end-result of the Rio summit called to focus on conservation policy on biological diversity, species extinction and ecosystem loss (Jeffries, 1997). It refers to all species of plants, animals and micro-organisms existing and interacting within an ecosystem (Vandermeer and Perfecto, 1995). Jeffries (1997) described it as the richness and variety of life on earth. He went further by defining it as an area of science which describes and measures diversity and simultaneously offering explanations on how these diversities are created since biodiversity is not homogeneously distributed throughout the world (Gaston, 2000 and 2005).

Biodiversity performs many ecological services. In natural ecosystems, the vegetative cover of a forest or grassland prevents soil erosion, replenishes ground water and controls flooding by enhancing infiltration and reducing water runoff (Perry, 1994). In agricultural systems, biodiversity performs ecosystem services beyond production of food, fibre, fuel, and income. Examples include recycling of nutrients, control of local microclimate, regulation of local hydrological processes, regulation of the abundance of undesirable organisms, and detoxification of noxious chemicals (Costanza *et al*, 1993). These renewal processes and ecosystem services are largely biological; therefore their persistence depends upon maintenance of biological diversity (Altieri, 1994 and 1999). When these natural services are lost due to biological simplification, the economic and environmental costs can be quite significant.

Biodiversity is not only an ethical and aesthetic inheritance for future generations. It provides a genetic bank that is essential to medical, agricultural and other scientific progress; most importantly, it plays a basic role in the ecosystem functions. Ecosystem functions provide, directly or indirectly, the ecosystem services to the human population, such as climate and water regulation, waste treatment, nutrient cycling, food production, genetic resources, and recreation (Costanza *et al*, 1993). Ecosystem services are critical to the functioning of the Planet's life-support systems, provide a basic contribution to human welfare, and are part of the total economic value of the planet (Costanza *et al*, 1997).

This reviewed paper discusses and summarise the following issues:

- Role of biodiversity in the ecosystem;
- Place of forest in the ecosystem;
- Impact of biodiversity loss on the forest ecosystem and;
- Mitigation measures.

ROLE OF BIODIVERSITY IN THE ECOSYSTEM

Biodiversity has three main dimensions: genetic variation within species and populations; the number of species; and habitat preservation (Srivastava *et al*, 1996). It is an index of species richness. To protect species

and genetically-distinct populations of each species, it is needful to preserve their environment as species cannot last if its environment is destroyed or seriously damaged (Srivastava *et al.*, 1996). Species habitats are the building blocks on which human livelihoods depend and also the foundation for forests, fisheries, and agricultural crops with their diversity and abundance determining the quality of urban life (Savard *et al.*, 2000). Habitat conservation issue is bordered on protecting the natural habitats for wild species and populations and simultaneously managing cultural habitats or environments modified for human use, such as urbanisation (Srivastava *et al.*, 1996).

Biodiversity includes all form of life (Savard *et al.*, 2000) and supports every aspect of human life. It provides a huge volume of ecosystem services also to urban residents, helping to buffer against nuisances generated by cities themselves. When biodiversity is lost, the strength and capacity of the ecosystems to provide essential goods and services become incapacitated in terms of scientific, educational, historical and cultural resources (Marten *et al.*, 2003).

PLACE OF FOREST IN THE ECOSYSTEM

Forests cover approximately 30% of the Earth's land surface and provide critical ecosystem goods and services, including food, fodder, water, shelter, nutrient cycling, and cultural and recreational value. The Rio Conventions: the United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change (UNFCCC), the United Nations Convention on Biological Diversity (CBD) and the United Nations Convention to Combat Desertification (UNCCD), all acknowledge the important contribution of forests to the achievement of their respective goals and objectives and are working together to enhance synergies in this area. Forests also store carbon, provide habitat for a wide range of species and help alleviate land degradation and desertification.

Forests are one of the most biodiversity-rich habitats on Earth. For example, approximately 60% of all higher plant species are based in rainforests. Furthermore, in the Amazon basin alone, more than 1,300 species of forest plants are used for medicinal or cultural purposes. This is one example of the vast array of forest biodiversity that has important value as a source of food, medicine, fodder, and raw material. As such, the achievement of the Millennium Development Goals is inextricably linked to forest biodiversity. It also provides almost 1.6 billion people with food, medicines, fuel and other basic necessities.

IMPACT OF BIODIVERSITY LOSS ON THE FOREST ECOSYSTEM

The Convention on Biological Diversity (CBD) which is an offshoot of the UNCED (Rio) summit of June 1992 signalled global recognition of the alarming loss of biodiversity, as well as the awareness of its values. The Convention came into force in December 1993, and was signed by the European Union (EU) and its member states, including Nigeria. CBD affirms that conservation of biodiversity is a common concern of humankind, and gives the following definition: "Biological diversity (or biodiversity) means the variability among living organisms from all sources including, inter alia, terrestrial, marine and other aquatic ecosystems and the complexes of which they are part; this includes diversity within species, between species and of ecosystems". The EU created several initiatives and agreements to consolidate the CBD in order to reverse the depletion of diversity in Europe (e.g., the Habitats Directive).

Forests are biologically diverse systems but are however increasingly threatened as a result of deforestation, fragmentation, climate change and other stressors that can be linked to human activities. The latest deforestation rates are estimated around 13 million hectares per year: a net loss of about 7.3 million hectares per year for 2000—2005 while by 2010 it was in the range of 3.4 million hectares for Africa (FAO, 2010). Deforestation is estimated to have been the cause of 20% of annual greenhouse gas emissions in the 1990s and even afterwards (Rhett, 2005.); Millenium Ecosystem Assessment, 2005; IPCC, Fourth Assessment Report, (2007). Climate change, in particular, is expected to impact on forest biodiversity and the ability of forests to provide soil and water protection, habitat for species and other ecosystem services.

Forest ecosystems identified as being particularly vulnerable to the impacts of climate change include: mangroves, boreal forests, tropical forests, cloud forests and dry forests. The potential negative impacts of climate change on dry forests are of particular concern since dry forest soils are particularly susceptible to wind and water erosion. According to the Millennium Ecosystem Assessment, drylands occupy 41% of the earth's land area and are home to more than 2 billion people. Intensive human intervention, for example, fire, grazing, agriculture, firewood collection, has adversely transformed many dry forests. Those dry forest systems that have

not been completely destroyed are generally impoverished and fragmented. The degradation process thus initiated has led to a shift away from the original vegetation types to drier, less productive and less resistant forest types, exposing large numbers of people to the threat of desertification and associated disastrous ecological, social, and economic impacts. On the other hand, there is evidence that primary forests and forests that are adequately managed for diversity and multiple benefits are more resilient to disturbances. These ecosystems maintain healthy, stable soils, provide natural habitats for forest biodiversity and provide a more stable store of carbon. In fact very often, forests with high biodiversity are mature primary forests which require fewer inputs to maintain standing biomass and soil carbon content.

Amongst the ecosystem services supported by biodiversity is climate regulation. One effect of the conversion of forests to agricultural production, for example, is an increase in carbon emissions from land clearance and a decrease in sequestered carbon. Both effects increase the rate of climate change (URL¹). When trees grow again on the deforested land, they are replaced by fast growth trees, which have a reduced ability to uptake Carbon (IV) oxide compared to the slow growth forests. This loss reduces biodiversity and contributes to global warming or climate change (Vandermeer and Perfecto, 1995). Biodiversity is also related to global warming. Slow growth forests can take in a significant amount of Carbon (IV) oxide but deforestation immediately cuts the contribution to this important environmental function.

One of today's societal challenges is the protection of natural benefits that fauna and flora provide to man by stopping the loss of biodiversity (Winter *et al.*, 2010). A major reason for this trend, i.e. decrease in biodiversity, is habitat degradation and its eventual loss. Forest management practices often favour tree plantations with non-native tree species and prefer homogenous forests. Consequently, lack of deadwood, natural gaps with pioneer species and structural heterogeneity in forest stands result in reduced forest biodiversity. It is therefore agreed that forest management that mimics natural processes and states of virgin forests stops the on-going loss in biodiversity.

MITIGATION MEASURES

One of the underlying principles for CBD is the ecosystem approach, a strategy for integrated management of land, air, water and living resources that advances conservation and sustainable use in an equitable way at the same time recognising that people are an integral part of the ecosystems (URL²). The Rio convention had three major goals: the preservation of biological diversity; the sustainable use of resources; and the equitable distribution of benefits arising from the use of genetic resources (URL²; Alexander, 2008). Alexander recognised that biological diversity can be a product of both natural processes and the combination of natural and human influences, implying that semi-natural habitat is important even though living things, including man, form a community by interacting with one another and also with the three media namely: air, water and soil in individual ecosystems.

Preserving biodiversity is costly but the importance of maintaining a wide variety of species makes the effort worthwhile. The establishment of national parks are laudable in preserving forests and biodiversity; however, not all land can be protected using this method. In ensuring sustainability of the ecosystem, there exists a trade-off in the triple bottom line of economy, environment and social demands as described by Elkington (1997) in his book '*Cannibals with Fork*'. People need space to live, farm and play which means some deforestation must occur. Also, trees are cut down for both economic and consumer benefits. Members of society need to determine how much economic cost they are willing to spend in preserving plant and animal species. Vandermeer and Perfecto (1995) argued that fewer additional species are protected as more land is protected. This suggests that a reasonable amount of protected land would preserve biodiversity while also leaving enough land to develop. Corporation could preserve biodiversity by finding sustainable methods for their use of resources. Biodiversity would benefit from individuals who choose to live in areas that have already been developed, reducing the need to clear additional forests. Tax incentives could be given to companies that find alternatives to deforestation. According to the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (2007), the conservation and restoration of forests can considerably reduce emissions at a low cost and with potential co benefits for adaptation and sustainable development. Further co-benefits can be achieved when steps to combat land degradation and conserve biodiversity are included in forest conservation and restoration.

For example in the United Kingdom, United Kingdom biodiversity action plan (UKBAP) is the government's framework for conserving biodiversity; this lies within the international framework which includes

commitments under the Convention for Biological Diversity and European Union (URL³). The UKBAP complements 'One future – different paths', the UK's framework for sustainable development, which recognises the importance of living within environmental limits in order to conserve biodiversity. It sets out an approach to biodiversity conservation that is designed not only to meet the commitment to halt the loss of biodiversity by 2010, but to guide action well into the second decade of the 21st century at a time when the challenges faced by the natural environment are great (URL³).

In Nigeria, efforts are being made at the national, state and local levels to stop the negative trends happening in our biodiversity. Non-governmental organisations such as the Nigerian Conservation Fund are not left behind. The efforts may seem minimal but the long-run results would be better appreciated.

CONCLUSION

Changes in biodiversity today are attributed to the rapid rate at which the climate is ever changing. Imbalance in biodiversity has effects on the ecosystems as can be garnered from the above written piece. The situation within the forest ecosystem is a pointer to what is simultaneously going on other ecosystems e.g. the marine ecosystem. Forests play an important part in climate change mitigation. Forests store a vast amount of carbon. When a forest is cut down and converted to another use, carbon is released back into the atmosphere.

Biodiversity has been described as the richness and variety of life on earth, therefore, this is the time to halt this process because man is also part of the biodiversity that is threatened and our failure to rise to the task is tantamount to the destruction of mankind as we have known it. Let us all join hands together and stop this trend.

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